

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF ASYMMETRIC BEHAVIOR OF PROPELLER SHAFTS DURING MANEUVERING OF TWIN SCREW SHIP

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Summary

The complexity and accuracy of numerical model describing the interaction between the elements in the system “Main engine-Hull-propeller-Rudder” are crucial in implementing the preset maneuvers both within model tests and practice. Models describing the interaction of the elements in this system are still improves and are not fully available. Such a simulation model would help in clarifying and defining the behavior of screws and rudders of the ship with twin propeller-twin rudder system, in avoiding overloading of one of the screw shafts, in predicting thrust and torque, and also to be analyzed more easily maneuverable propulsion characteristics of the propeller. This allows even at the design stage, if it’s necessary resizing propeller shaft or recalculation, and choice of better suited propeller-rudder system.

Keywords: maneuverability, twin screw ship, propulsion system, thrust, torque.

1.INTRODUCTION

The adopted resolution of IMO related to safe navigation, led to increased requirements and maneuver standards, which are estimate the ship maneuverability. The shipowners and shipbuilders are already very interested in developing of methods and studies for simulation models to predict the behavior of the ship and the crew itself to be more prepared. Many studies have been developed over the years on this topic, but few of them are focused on the twin-screw ships, it is a reason for serious lack of information and difficulties for designers working in this field. Generally, it is well-known that the system “propeller shafts – steering gear ” could experience significant power fluctuations during critical maneuvers [1, 2, 3, 4]. Moreover, in the case of twin-screw ship, the two shafts in dynamic mode can have a significant asymmetric behavior and imbalances of power and torque. According to previous studies related to the propeller’s efficiency, two influence factors have been identified - the oblique flow and the wake fraction [4, 5]. In practice, especially for high-speed twin-screw

ships, have been reported cases of overloading of one of the screws and its shaft, leading to critical damage and the risk of collisions.

2.EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The problem of the asymmetric load of the system “propeller shafts – steering gear“ with two screws and two rudders can be seen when performing critical curvilinear maneuvers, especially at high speeds. Under these conditions, the influence of the local angle of attack of the flow at the propeller zone and the wake in the rudder area is noticeable, which would affect to their effectiveness. Researching of this problem, led to the preparation and conducting of maneuvering tests by an autonomous ship model with a twin screw - twin rudder system. A series of tests in two speeds was conducted (cruising and maximum): circulation on port and starboard side with variation of the rudder angle and "maneuver Williamson" [1, 2, 3, 4, 6].

The model is equipped with 2 screws provided by the BSHC (*fig.1, 2 and 3*). Main characteristics are described in *Table 1 and 2*.

TABLE 1. Main particulars of hull

Non-dimensional hull data	Symbol	Values
Length to beam ratio	L_{PP}/B	6,269
Beam to draft ratio	B/T	3,395
Rudder lateral area	A_R/LT	0,011
Block coefficient	C_B	0,460
Number propellers	[-]	2
Number rudders	[-]	2

Fig. 1. **3D** hull model view

TABLE 2. Propeller model data

Propellers	№ 1	№ 2
D, mm	110,3	110,3
P/D at 0.7R	1,04	1,04
A_E/A_0	0,446	0,446
Number blades	4	4
Direction of rotation	Right handed	Left handed

Fig. 2. Propeller

Fig. 3. View of rudder – propeller arrangement

Experimental program

The maneuvering model tests were carried out at BSHC Maneuvering & Seakeeping Basin (*fig.5*) with main dimensions $L \times B \times T = 60 \text{ m} \times 40 \text{ m} \times 2.5 \text{ m}$ maximum depth. (*fig.4*), at an initial steady speed, deep calm water and constant revolutions [7].

Fig. 4. Maneuvering basin main dimensions

Fig. 5. Maneuvering basin

Fig. 6. Thrust and torque dynamometer

Thrust and torque load measurement is provided by screw dynamometer connected to the screw shaft (*fig.6*). Since the measurement is done on the shaft of one of the screws, in order to trace the asymmetric load between the two propellers, the circulations of the experimental program are provided for the two boards. Thus, it appears to be "external" or "inward" located.

Table 3. Program for autonomous maneuvering tests

Maneuver	Model initial speed [m/s]	Fr [-]	Rudder angle [deg]
Turning	1.9; 2.48	0.34;0.44	20, 25,30,35
Williamson turn	1.9; 2.48	0.34;0.44	$\delta = 35^\circ \rightarrow \psi=60/$ $\delta = -35^\circ \rightarrow \psi=180$
Steering gear test	1.9; 2.48	0.34;0.44	35°/-35°

2. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

2.1. Factors reflecting the asymmetric shaft's load

During movement of the multiple screw vessel in a curved trajectory, the local drift angle in the rudder and propeller area, in particular twin screw is different because the radii of rotation due to the propeller position along the ship. It's possible significantly asymmetric behavior of the two propellers, which can affect at its torque, thrust and power respectively and also to lead to increasing their values according to initial movement at the straight course [8, 9, 10].

When the ship moves in the original straight course with nominal propeller's revolutions n_0 and nominal speed V_0 , the running mode is fully characterized by the advance coefficient $J_0=V_0.(1-w)/D.n_0$ and the thrust and

torque coefficients K_{T0} , K_{Q0} , respectively. Upon entering at the curvilinear maneuver, conditions in propeller's zone are changed [5, 7].

In the case of curvilinear motion with a drift angle β , the character of the hull flow varies, respectively, the wake fraction w . As the local drift angle β_K increases, w decreases and reaches zero at limit values of the β and angular speed \bar{r} [1, 3, 4, 6, 7]:

$$w' = w \cdot f(\beta, \bar{r}),$$

$f_w(\beta, \bar{r})$ - a function dependent on the motion of the ship - the drift angle and the angular velocity

The asymmetric thrust and torque load at the twin-screw ships may be explained by the change of the local drift angle β_K and wake fraction w . The influence of β at w is fundamentally differs for both sides. The wake fraction w depends on the advance coefficient J and the thrust and torque coefficients K_T, K_Q :

$$(1) \quad K_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4} \quad \text{- thrust coefficient,}$$

$$(2) \quad K_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D^5} \quad \text{- torque coefficient.}$$

The wake fraction w in the system "propeller shafts – steering gear" is asymmetric, if it is considered separately for each the propeller's area. In a curvilinear motion, the speed at the corresponding point where the propeller is located is important, and it is affected by the angular velocity. For this purpose it is necessary tracking the speeds, i.e. the velocity vectors in the points where the propellers are located:

$$(3) \quad r = \frac{V}{R}$$

The layout describing the velocity vector for the two boards respectively and their dependence on angular velocity, the speed of the ship at its center of gravity, and the local drift angles are illustrated in *fig.7*.

Fig. 7. Coordinate system for speed vectors

2.2.RESULTS

At *fig.8* are presented comparative results of the maneuvering test with different Froude numbers - 0.34 ($U = 1.9$ m/s) and 0.44 ($U = 2.48$ m/s). It's noticeable the asymmetric behavior of the screws for its thrust and torque. Whether the internal propeller is wrapping at a low or higher speed, it is slightly overloaded. Also, the rudder's deflection angle, i.e. the local angle of attack does not significantly affect at the internal screw. The external screws are with asymmetric behavior about the thrust and torque, it may be due to the local drift angle, or here the wake fraction there is a larger role due to the different flow velocity.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. T/T_0 – turning $\delta=20$ and 35 degrees, $Fr=0.34$ and 0.44

Figure 9 shows large overload of the "outer" propeller and the tendency to increase almost double at the largest rudder's angles of circulation. It is noteworthy, that if at small rudder angle, the "internal" screw is not too overloaded, at the big rudder angle it is overloaded, regardless of speed.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Q/Q_0 – turning $\delta=20$ and 35 degrees, $Fr=0.34$ and 0.44

Figure 10 shows how the local drift angle is reflected at the asymmetric load and the smaller role of the wake fraction in the area of the corresponding system “propeller shafts – steering gear”. This effect is clearly noticed with the “outer” screw, since it is external to the center of the circulation and the angle of attack is smaller.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. T/T_0 – turning $\delta=20$ and 35 degrees, $Fr=0.34$ and 0.44

At the *fig.11*, the torque load results for the two screws are compared at the same speed. At both speeds, the "outer" screw is overloaded, especially at the largest rudder angle, but they notice that larger values are measured at low speed. It is also noticeable, that the "internal" screw, in the unsteady stage of circulation is overloaded also.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Q/Q_0 – turning $\delta=20$ and 35 degrees, $Fr=0.34$ and 0.44

Williamson's maneuvers were conducted on two Froude numbers (*Fig.12*). It is clearly noticeable the asymmetric loading of the screw in the transition of its role from "internal" to "external", relative to the center of rotation of the ship. There is no clear asymmetric load as for circulating at different Froude numbers (*Fig.13*).

Fig. 12. Trajectory at Williamson turn

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13. T/T_0 – Williamson turn, $Fr=0.34; 0.44$

The test results show that, when the Williamson maneuver is performed, the overloading of the drivers is not greater than 40%, and also than at the high rudder angles of deflection.

3. CONCLUSION

In the framework of this study, experiments were conducted, at which circulations with different rudder angles were varied. Also are fulfilled critical maneuvers, like to rescue a person. These tests were performed at a high and low speed. The results confirmed the danger of maneuvering on a curved trajectory by a significant asymmetric behavior of the two propellers by torque, thrust and power, respectively, and to overloading up to 60% of the nominal values at a steady straight course [1,3,4,6]. This could be helpfully for development of an algorithm which, on the basis of conducted tests, will estimate the influence of the two main factors - the oblique flow and wake fraction in the zones where are located each of the two propellers [2,8,9]. Such research through could help to determine the effectiveness of each of the rudders and to obtain more complete information about the interaction of the elements in the system "propeller shafts – steering gear ", which will be useful in the design of fast twin-screw and twin-rudder ships.

AWARENESS

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